

Development and Practical Application of Digital Twins

FELIP WANG

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Abstract

This research explores the application of Digital Twin (DT) technology in Facility Management (FM) by implementing Autodesk Tandem and Tandem Connect. The study was conducted in collaboration with IBE d.d. and focused on improving their existing FM system, which currently utilizes IoT devices and a 2D digital monitoring platform. The research aims to enhance real-time data access, stakeholder engagement, and Indoor Environment Quality (IEQ) by integrating a DT model that accurately represents building assets and operational processes. The research established three dimensions: foundational, implementational, and outcome assessment. The foundational dimension involves reviewing current DT applications in FM and defining specific requirements and research goals. The implementational dimension takes advantage of the FM system and brings its management thinking into the DT platform implementation. Moreover, it tests connectivity with IoT devices and analyzes the DT platform's capabilities. The final dimension assesses the effectiveness of the DT implementation, identifies additional functionalities, and provides recommendations for future improvements.

Overall, the implementation of Autodesk Tandem and Tandem Connect demonstrates signifi-

cant potential in enhancing FM practices through improved data visualization and real-time monitoring. However, challenges related to timestamp accuracy, system configuration, and documentation were identified, highlighting areas for further development. The research concludes by outlining the successful realization of its goals while emphasizing the need for ongoing refinement and exploration of DT technology in FM.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/S8irXun4A0w>

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